

The Theory of Generations as a Tool for the Formation of Motivation among Employees on the Example of the Strategic Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Alieva Zarina Albinovna¹

¹ Primary school teachers at NOU Leader, Uzbekistan, Tashkent city

Abstract:

The article reveals the basic concepts of the theory of generations. An analysis of the features and differences of both previous generations and more modern representatives of the generation was carried out, thanks to which practical recommendations were derived in the field of motivation and development of modern society in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: theory of generations, differences between generations, motivation, values, stimulation.

The large-scale reforms carried out over the years of independence have laid a solid foundation for national statehood and sovereignty, ensuring security and law and order, inviolability of state borders, the rule of law, human rights and freedoms, interethnic harmony and religious tolerance in society, created decent living conditions for the population and the realization of the creative potential of citizens.

Rejection of administrative and command management of the economy, phased implementation of market reforms and a prudent monetary policy contributed to ensuring macroeconomic stability, high economic growth rates, keeping inflation within forecast limits, creating broad opportunities

and favourable conditions for the development of small businesses and private entrepreneurship, the farming movement.

At the same time, a comprehensive analysis of the past stage of the country's development, the changing situation in the world economy in the context of globalization and increasing competition require the development and implementation of radically new ideas and principles for further sustainable and advanced development of the country. [2]

Today, many companies are faced with the fact that the motivation, values and desired working conditions of young employees are fundamentally different from their predecessors. More and more modern companies are concluding that it is necessary to transform existing approaches, methods and management tools.

The idea of the existence of certain generational cycles that replace each other approximately every 20 years is described in the Theory of Generations. The essence of the theory is that people born in a certain period of time, falling under the influence of socio-cultural factors, have similar values, patterns of behavior and even thinking.

“The Generation Theory” was developed by the Americans William Strauss and Neil Howe. Their first book on the subject, *Generations*, was published in 1991. The next book, *The Fourth Turning*, published in 1997, developed the theory. The authors wrote about four particular generational cycles and repetitive patterns of generational behavior in US history. [5]

This theory can be applied in personnel management and assume that the labor market is updated every 20 years with the advent of a new generation. At the same time, each generation has its own individual set of personal qualities and values, and is also formed in a special socio-historical context. Based on this, modern companies may have different approaches to the selection of employees, their training, motivation, etc. It should be noted that the theory of generations was positively received by representatives of the field of personnel management in countries such as the USA, Russia, etc.

Western consultants identify four generations: [4, p.10]

Generation Y (born 1985–2000)	Generation X (born 1965–1984)	Baby Boomer generation (born 1943–1965)	Silent generation (born 1923–1945)
Their values:	Their values:	Their values:	Their values:
changes; optimism; sociability; self confidence; diversity; creation; freelancing, remote office, flexible working hours; loose clothing at work; achievement; immediate reward; morality, morality; civic duty; technical, computer competence	changes; choice; equality; individualism; competition, survival; self-reliance; pragmatism; global awareness; lifelong learning; technical, computer competence; free ("denim") Friday; unisex.	optimism; youth; health; Job; team orientation; personal growth, striving to be the best; personal reward and status; official dress code at work; gender attractiveness.	honor; law and order; compliance with the rules; devotion; respect for position and status; sacrifice; patience; economy; religiosity (or partisanship).

The theory of generations is a good tool for forming the values of corporate culture, as well as for choosing channels for conveying information to representatives of different generations when introducing a system of incentives and motivation.

Motivation and stimulation is the process of satisfying a physiological, psychological or social need, which activates behavior and creates an incentive aimed at achieving a certain reward (obtaining certain benefits) through labor activity. [3, p.80]

Generation X Ways of motivation	Career growth
	Flexible working hours
	Praise
	Tuition Fees, Discounts, Additional promotions

Generation Y Ways of motivation	Flexible Free work schedule
	Not being able to do the work at home
	The opportunity to express your opinion
	Rewards for achievement

Generation Z Ways of motivation	The prospect of an increase
	Wage growth
	Free work schedule
	Public gratitude

The silent Generation values	Optimism, striving for joy. The need for good health
	Patriotism, pride in the country, feeling like the best. Respect for laws, order, rules and standards.
	Striving for stability. Acceptance of social and family values.

For a mature professional aged 46–60 and over, the most significant motivational factor is the stability of the company and the stability of its position in it. Also an important motivational factor for mature staff is a social package and health support. A comfortable atmosphere and positive relationships with colleagues are important for mature employees, they strive to be essential to the business. [4, p.16]

In April 2018, in response to the call of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to compatriots living abroad to be involved in large-scale reforms carried out in our country, the International Non-Governmental Non-Profit Organization "Buyuk Kelajak" or "Great Future" was created.

Under the banner of the new organization, the efforts of all those people who would like to support the ongoing transformations in Uzbekistan, the comprehensive development of the state and society were united. The main intellectual asset of INNO "Buyuk Kelajak" was the Expert Council, created in a few months, consisting of leading specialists from various industries - immigrants from Uzbekistan, living and studying abroad, practicing abroad, carrying out their professional activities in Uzbekistan.

To achieve its goals international non-governmental non-profit organization

"Buyuk Kelajak" at this stage carries out the following tasks: [1]

1. Development of the concept of the development strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
2. Assistance in the implementation of the long-term development model of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2035.
3. Development of a roadmap for the implementation of a strategy for a long-term development model of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2035.
4. Providing comprehensive expert support to the ongoing reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan within the framework of the action strategy in five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021.

There are 4 types of scenarios for the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

- evolutionary scenario - a favorable external environment with unsuccessful implementation of reforms;
- pessimistic scenario – negative external environment and external crises with unsuccessful implementation of reforms;
- dynamic scenario – reforms are carried out under favorable external conditions and a significant amount of investment;
- progressive scenario - reforms are carried out in a negative external environment and external crises.

Of course, Uzbekistan will develop in any scenario, but a dynamic scenario is preferable, because, under it, by 2035, the volume of GDP will increase 10 times and the country will enter the top 50 countries in terms of GDP. [1]

To achieve this goal, special attention should be paid to the features and characteristics of modern society, taking into account the theory we have described, taking it as a methodological basis. In this regard, the theory says that for generation Z it is possible to use methods that are suitable for both generation X and generation Y.

Material motivation methods will have a strong impact, but non-material motivation methods suitable for stimulating representatives of this generation are more in number. This suggests that more nuances should be taken into account in the field of non-material motivation.

Thus, we can conclude that the needs of generation Z can largely be satisfied by the methods that were used to motivate representatives of generations X and Y.

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